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Report on the optimization procedure and technical layout of efficient moderator assemblies

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ABSTRACT

This work reports the optimisation procedure and the numerical investigation of the Cold Source moderator in the spallation neutron source SINQ at PSI, Switzerland, one of the main European infrastructures for neutron-based material science. The investigation confirms that the energy deposition from the SINQ target is not large enough to operate the Cold Source moderator just by using the heat deposit by the secondary particles produced by the beam. This is an important outcome as it paves the way to a new moderator design, which would increase the efficiency of SINQ by up to 50 % as theoretical studies predicted, without increasing the energy consumption. Guidelines for a new moderator design are presented as well in this work. It leads to the conclusion

that the performance of the new moderator should be independent of the beam current as it has several advantages. A first concept of such a moderator is presented, which was already optimized regarding its gain in neutron flux but needs to be studied by CFD simulations. Plans to use a more accurate multiphase model with the optimized geometries are considered.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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REPORT ON THE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE AND TECHNICAL LAYOUT OF EFFICIENT MODERATOR ASSEMBLIES

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Executive summary

This work deals with the numerical investigation of the cold source moderator in the spallation neutron source SINQ at PSI. In Chapter 1. the historical development of the cold source moderator is described. After its commissioning, it became clear that the measured neutron yield provided by the moderator was not as good as the one expected from the simulations. The aim of this work is to investigate the reason for this mismatch.

In the Chapter 2. the numerical method of RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes) is described. For the single-phase simulation of the cold source moderator, the k - ϵ -turbulence model with the near wall formulation of the Wall Function (WF) are used.

Chapter 3. explain how the moderator is built, given particular emphasis to the AlMg3 moderator chamber as well as the “re-entrant box”.

In Chapter 4. the discretisation of the moderator is described.

A main part of this work is the explanation of the spatially resolved energy deposition from Monte-Carlo simulations given in Chapter 5. and its use in the CFD-Code ANSYS Fluent. This energy deposition is programmed as current dependent User Defined Functions (UDFs).

In Chapter 6. the temperature dependent material data of the used material are displayed, especially for the case of Deuterium in the cryogenic boundary conditions between ~ 18 K and ~ 38 K.

Chapter 7. presents the analysis of the CFD-simulation together with the employed boundary conditions. The simulations show that the energy deposition for the liquid and vapour Deuterium phase at the maximum beam current at SINQ target is not large enough in order for the Deuterium to evaporate. The investigation on the surrounding AlMg3 moderator chamber shows that, at a proton beam current of 1.5 mA, not enough energy is deposited.

In Chapter 8. different possible options for an increasing the effectiveness of the moderator are presented. Some options deals with increasing of the energy deposition on the moderator, others with a direct internal heating concept for evaporating the liquid deuterium in the Re-Entrant Hole. And still others present direct integrated Re-Entrant Holes in the moderator. In the focus of the considerations is how one can become independent from the beam current and the associated phase change of the deuterium. On this basis, the advantages and disadvantages of the individual proposals were examined.

Chapter 9. summarizes this investigation with the main conclusion that the energy deposition from the SINQ target is not large enough for operating the cold source moderator under the expected conditions. As the analysis shows a solution is feasible that is much less sensitive to varying proton beam intensity. In particular, two suggestions stand out with directly integrated Re-Entrant Hols in the moderator. Moreover, future plans to use a more accurate multiphase model with optimized geometries are presented.

1. Introduction

In a spallation neutron source the neutrons generated in the spallation target must be moderated to a lower energy range, useful for neutron scattering experiments or neutron radiography. Usually at a spallation source, there are neutrons with thermal and cold spectrum available, ultracold neutrons are exceptionally. They are generated by collisions of neutrons with a gas or liquid at thermal or cold temperatures, which is called the moderator. After many collisions, their energy spectrum is determined by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution at the temperature of the moderator. Thermal neutrons have energies around 25 meV, cold neutrons less than 5 meV, often given in equivalent wavelengths of Angstroms. The moderator efficiency is a key element in the chain of converting the initial proton beam intensity to the desired neutron spectrum with sufficient flux at the experiments. In this work the optimization of the cryogenic D₂ moderator system of SINQ is studied.

The SINQ moderator system has operated since the start-up of SINQ in the year 1997. The moderator vessel contains about 20 liter of liquid D₂ at a temperature of around 25 K. It supplies cold neutrons to a neutron guide systems serving 13 experimental stations. Since 2003 the original moderator was replaced by a new version with a single re-entrant hole (or also called beam window) on the neutron guide side. For this new moderator version an intensity gain was predicted for the guide-system of about 1.2 at 2 Å rising to a maximum of 1.9 for neutrons of wavelength 9 Å and longer. Later, recent studies by R. Bergman resulted in a maximum gain factor of 1.5 with an optimized moderator [1].

Measurements performed after restarting SINQ operation showed that the predicted value could not be reached [2]. The likely reason that the re-entrant hole is not emptied was assumed but never proofed. However, a precise understanding is necessary before the moderator can be redesigned to reach the predicted gain factor. This would directly increase the efficiency of the target station, i.e. the cold neutron flux, without increasing the energy consumption. In principle, the beam power could be reduced by this factor to save energy, or vice versa, the quality of the measurements could be improved or the number of measurements could be increased.

Therefore, the goal of this work is to understand the reason for the failure of the present moderator design by simulating the operation performance with the numerical method of the Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD). The CFD is combined with Monte-Carlo simulations. The distribution of the energy deposition for the moderator components is calculated by MCNP6.1, a particle transport Monte Carlo simulation. The energy distribution is implemented in the CFD-Code via an User Defined Function (UDF). With this energy deposition the temperature distribution in the different parts of the moderator are calculated, which allows then a trend of the operational behaviour.

2. Basics of Fluid Mechanics

2.1 NUMERIC NOTATION

In this report the „Einstein-Notation“ index is used and summation signs are omitted for clarity; summation is done over repeated indices.

$$\frac{d}{dt}\rho + \frac{d}{dx_i}(\rho u_i) = \frac{d}{dt}\rho + \frac{d}{dx}(\rho u_x) + \frac{d}{dy}(\rho u_y) + \frac{d}{dz}(\rho u_z) = 0$$

As example $x_i (i = 1,2,3)$ represents (x, y, z) in the Cartesian coordinates. Similarly, u_i or (u_x, u_y, u_z) describes the Cartesian components of the velocity vector [3].

2.2 CONSERVATION EQUATION

The fluid mechanics describes the state of a fluid by conservation equations. The conservation equations for mass, momentum and energy are balanced in a control volume (KV). First, the rate of change of mass m is considered [4]. The mass in the flow can neither be generated nor destroyed so that

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = 0$$

The conservation of momentum can be represented by the second Newton's law of motion:

$$\frac{d(mu)}{dt} = EQ \sum F$$

where u is the velocity and F is the sum of surface and body forces acting on the system. In the fluid mechanic analysis it isn't advisable to consider a control mass (KM) instead of a control volume (KV). A general transport equation can be introduced by considering a scalar quantity ϕ in a control volume [3] [4]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V_{KM}} \phi \rho V dV = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{V_{KV}} \phi \rho V dV + \int_{S_{KV}} \phi \rho S (u - u_b) \cdot n dS$$

where V describes the control volume, S is the surface of the control volume, n the unit vector normal to the surface S , u is the fluid velocity and u_b the surface velocity.

2.2.1 Continuity Equation

The continuity equation can be described using the above equation by an integral formulation, with $\phi = 1$.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho V dV + \int_S \rho u \cdot n dS = 0$$

The surface integral is transformed to a convective term of a volume integral by using the Gauss-Theorem. However, this requires that the control volume can be infinitely small. This leads to the continuity equation in differential form [3]:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\rho + \nabla(\rho u) = 0$$

2.2.2 Momentum Equation

In the momentum equation affected forces (surface and body forces) on the control volume are considered.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho u dV + \int_S \rho u u \cdot n dS = \sum F$$

With the introduction of the stress tensor T for Newtonian fluids, the molecular transport rate of the momentum is represented by [3]:

$$T = -\left(p + \frac{2}{3} \nabla \cdot u\right) I + 2\mu D$$

This stress tensor T is composed of the dynamic viscosity μ , the unit tensor I , the static pressure p and deformation rate tensor D :

$$D = \frac{1}{2} [\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T]$$

With the body force b included, the integral form of the momentum equation is obtained [3].

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho u dV + \int_S \rho u u \cdot n dS = \int_S T \cdot n dS + \int_V \rho b dV$$

or the differential form of the momentum equation [5]

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\rho u) + \nabla(\rho u u) = \nabla \tau - \nabla p + \rho g$$

with the shear stress tensor τ , the pressure p and gravity g .

2.2.3 Energy Equation

The energy equation uses the internal and the external energy flows [4].

$$\frac{d}{dt}(K + E) = P + \dot{Q}$$

The internal energy E of the control volume is built as integral of the internal energy of a particle edm .

$$E = \int_V e\rho dV$$

The total energy also includes the kinetic energy K of the control volume and is defined as follows:

$$K = \int_V \frac{u^2}{2} \rho dV$$

External forces, e.g. the surface and volume forces, cause the power P at a control volume.

$$P = \int_S uT \cdot ndS + \int_V \rho ubdV$$

In addition also the supplied heat flow is added to the balance.

$$\dot{Q} = - \int_S \dot{q} \cdot ndS$$

The energy equation follows in integral notation [4].

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho \left(e + \frac{1}{2} u^2 \right) dV = \int_V \rho ubdV + \int_S (uT - \dot{q}) \cdot ndS$$

Analogously, the equation in differential form is:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\rho h) + \nabla(\rho uh) = -\nabla \vec{q} + \frac{d}{dt}p + \nabla(\tau u)$$

with the enthalpy h and the heat flux vector \vec{q} [5].

2.3 REYNOLDS-AVERAGED NAVIER STOKES (RANS)

A common method for the calculation of turbulent flows is the Reynolds-Averaged-Navier-Stokes (RANS) modeling. In this method, the entire transient flow is averaged.

Figure 1: Time-averaged representation of the statistical steady state flow [3].

Figure 1 shows a statistical steady state flow, which is plotted time-averaged. The single value ϕ can be described as a time-averaged value $\bar{\phi}$ with its fluctuation ϕ' .

$$\phi(x_i, t) = \bar{\phi}(x_i) + \phi'(x_i, t)$$

Integration over the averaging time interval T determines the value $\bar{\phi}(x_i)$. Compared to typical time scales of fluctuation this interval must be very large. For steady flows (with $\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} T$) $\bar{\phi}$ is independent of time [3].

$$\bar{\phi}(x_i) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \phi(x_i, t) dt$$

This type of averaging leads to the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations.

For the averaged continuity and momentum equation of an incompressible flow without body force it is:

$$\frac{d}{dx_i}(\rho u_i) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho u_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j + \overline{\rho u'_i u'_j}) = \frac{-\partial}{\partial x_i} \bar{p} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \bar{\tau}_{ij}$$

with the mean viscous stress tensor $\bar{\tau}_{ij}$.

$$\bar{\tau}_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \bar{u}_i + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \bar{u}_j \right)$$

Analogously, the mean value equation of a scalar quantity is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \bar{\phi}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho \bar{u}_j \bar{\phi} + \overline{\rho u'_j \phi'}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \bar{\phi} \right)$$

Since the Reynolds stresses $\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j}$ and the turbulent scalar fluxes $\overline{\rho u'_i \phi'}$ are unknown quantities, additional equations have to be introduced to the system of turbulence equations [3]. In literature, this

problem is referred to as closure problem. This closure problem is usually modelled with a gradient approach (Boussinesq approximation) and a turbulent viscosity coefficient μ_t [3].

For the Reynolds stresses $\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j}$ the following equation is valid

$$-\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j} = \mu_t \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \bar{u}_i + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \bar{u}_j \right) - \frac{2}{3} \rho \delta_{ij} k$$

where k describes the kinetic energy of turbulence.

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \overline{u'_i u'_i}$$

The turbulent scalar fluxes will $\overline{\rho u'_i \phi'}$ is closed with

$$-\overline{\rho u'_i \phi'} = \Gamma_t \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \bar{\phi}$$

where Γ_t describes the turbulent diffusivity of the scalar quantity.

The simplest description of the eddy viscosity μ_t can be defined by the fluctuation velocity u' and the length L [3]:

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu u' L$$

2.3.1 Turbulence-Models

Two-equation turbulence models allow the determination of a turbulent length and time scale by solving two separate transport equations.

2.3.1.1 Standard-k-ε-Model

The Standard-k-ε-Model [3] is based on two transport equations for the turbulence kinetic energy (k) and its dissipation rate (ϵ).

The fluctuation velocity u' can be replaced by the relationship of the turbulent kinetic energy, $u' = \sqrt{k}$ [3]. In the k-ε-turbulence model the eddy viscosity μ_t is then defined as follows:

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu u' L = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\epsilon}$$

The turbulent kinetic energy k is determined by the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \bar{u}_j k)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\mu \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\rho}{2} \overline{u'_j u'_i u'_i} + \overline{p' u'_j} \right) - \overline{\rho u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} - \mu \frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_k}$$

where $\left(\frac{\rho}{2}\overline{u'_j u'_i u'_i} + \overline{p' u'_j}\right)$ describes the turbulent diffusion of the kinetic energy. This term has to be modeled and the following approach is used:

$$-\left(\frac{\rho}{2}\overline{u'_j u'_i u'_i} + \overline{p' u'_j}\right) \approx \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j}$$

To determine the length L the so-called turbulent balance can be used, which is given by the following relationship [3]:

$$\varepsilon \approx \frac{k^{\frac{3}{2}}}{L}$$

Through this approach, the length L can be obtained with the following equation for the dissipation rate ε .

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\varepsilon)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho\bar{u}_j\varepsilon)}{\partial x_j} = C_\varepsilon P_k \frac{\varepsilon}{k} + \rho C_{\varepsilon 2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right)$$

The dissipation rate uses the model-specific constants C_μ , $C_{\varepsilon 1}$, $C_{\varepsilon 2}$, σ_k and σ_ε .

The production rate P_k is expressed as follows:

$$P_k = -\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j}$$

2.3.1.2 Standard-k- ω -Model

The Standard-k- ω -Model in ANSYS Fluent is based on the Wilcox-k- ω -Model [6], which incorporates modifications for low-Reynolds number effects, compressibility and shear flow spreading. One of the weak points of the Wilcox model is the sensitivity of the solutions to values for k and ω outside the shear layer (freestream sensitivity).

The Standard-k- ω -Model is an empirical model based on model transport equations for the turbulence kinetic energy k and the specific dissipation rate ω .

The transport equations are described for turbulence kinetic energy k

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i k)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k - Y_k + S_k$$

and the specific dissipation rate ω .

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\omega)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i \omega)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_\omega - Y_\omega + S_\omega$$

G_k describes the generation of turbulence kinetic energy due to mean velocity gradients and G_ω the generation of specific dissipation rate ω . Γ_k and Γ_ω represent the effective diffusivity of k and ω , while Y_k and Y_ω represent the dissipation of k and ω due to turbulence. S_k and S_ω are source terms.

The effective diffusivities for the Standard-k- ω -Model are formulated as

$$\Gamma_k = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k}$$

$$\Gamma_\omega = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\omega}$$

with the quantities σ_k and σ_ω for the turbulent Prandtl numbers of k and ω . The turbulent viscosity μ_t , is described as follows:

$$\mu_t = \alpha \frac{\rho k}{\omega}$$

The coefficient α damps the turbulent viscosity causing a Low-Reynolds number correction. It is given by

$$\alpha = \alpha_\infty \left(\frac{\alpha_0 + \frac{\Re_t}{R_k}}{1 + \frac{\Re_t}{R_k}} \right)$$

with

$$\Re_t = \frac{\rho k}{\mu \omega},$$

$$R_k = 6,$$

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{\beta_i}{3},$$

$$\beta_i = 0.072.$$

Note that in the High-Reynolds number form of the Standard-k- ω -Model $\alpha = \alpha_\infty = 1$.

2.3.1.3 Shear Stress Transport (SST) Model

The shear-stress transport (SST) k- ω -Model was developed by Menter [7] to effectively blend the robust and accurate formulation of the k- ω -Model in the near-wall region with the freestream

independence of the k-ε-Model in the far field. The SST k-ω-Model is similar to the Standard-k-ω-Model, but includes the following refinements:

- The Standard-k-ω-Model and transformed k-ε-Model are both multiplied by a blending function. Both models are added up. The blending function is designed to be one in the near-wall region, which activates the Standard-k-ω-Model, and zero away from the surface, which activates the transformed k-ε-Model.
- The SST model incorporates a damped cross-diffusion derivative term in the ω equation.
- The definition of the turbulent viscosity is modified to account for the transport of the turbulent shear stress.
- The modeling constants are different.

The SST k-ω-Model is similar to the Standard-k-ω-Model:

The transport equations are described for turbulence kinetic energy k

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i k)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k - Y_k + S_k$$

and the specific dissipation rate ω .

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \omega)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_j \omega)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_\omega - Y_\omega + D_\omega + S_\omega$$

G_k represents the generation of turbulence kinetic energy due to mean velocity gradients and G_ω the generation of specific dissipation rate ω . Γ_k and Γ_ω describe also the effective diffusivity of k and ω . Y_k and Y_ω describe the dissipation of k and ω due to turbulences. D_ω represents the cross-diffusion term. S_k and S_ω are source terms.

The effective diffusivities for the SST k-ω-Model are calculated by

$$\Gamma_k = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k}$$

$$\Gamma_\omega = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\omega}$$

with the quantities σ_k and σ_ω for the turbulent Prandtl numbers of k and ω :

$$\sigma_k = \frac{1}{\frac{F_1}{\sigma_{k,1}} + \frac{(1-F_1)}{\sigma_{k,2}}}$$

$$\sigma_\omega = \frac{1}{\frac{F_1}{\sigma_{\omega,1}} + \frac{(1-F_1)}{\sigma_{\omega,2}}}$$

The turbulent viscosity μ_t is described differently than in the k- ω -Model:

$$\mu_t = \frac{\rho k}{\omega} \frac{1}{\max\left[\frac{1}{\alpha}, \frac{SF_2}{a_1\omega}\right]}$$

with

$$\alpha = \alpha_\infty \left(\frac{\alpha_0 + \frac{\mathfrak{R}_t}{R_k}}{1 + \frac{\mathfrak{R}_t}{R_k}} \right)$$

S is the strain rate magnitude and F_1, F_2 are blending functions defined as:

$$F_1 = \tanh(\phi_1^4)$$

$$\phi_1 = \min$$

$$D_\omega^+ = \max\left[2\rho \frac{1}{\sigma_{\omega,2}} \frac{1}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j}, 10^{-10}\right]$$

$$F_2 = \tanh(\phi_2^2)$$

$$\phi_2 = \max\left[2 \frac{\sqrt{k}}{0.09\omega y}, \frac{500\mu}{\rho y^2 \omega}\right]$$

with the distance y next to the surface and D_ω^+ the positive part of the cross-diffusion term.

2.3.2 Near-Wall-Models

In the turbulent boundary layer, two different layers (Figure 2) arise. The distinction between the two layers is due to the different behaviour of the dynamic viscosity μ and the dynamic eddy viscosity μ_t with respect to the distance y from the wall. The dynamic viscosity μ is a constant fluid property, whereas the dynamic eddy viscosity μ_t strongly increases with increasing wall distance y [8].

Figure 2: Scheme of the turbulent boundary layers (left) and the representation of the universal velocity profile u^+ with respect to the dimensionless wall distance y^+ (right) [8].

Near the wall (Wandschicht δ_W) the molecular viscosity has a large effect. This means, that the dynamic viscosity μ and dynamic eddy viscosity μ_t are effective. Even in this so-called viscous sublayer (viskose Unterschicht) this influence dominates. In the so-called defect layer (Defektschicht δ) the dynamic eddy viscosity μ_t is dominant and the influence of the molecular viscosity is low [8].

For all turbulent boundary layers $\delta_W \ll \delta$ applies. With increasing Reynolds numbers the thickness of the wall layer δ_W is always smaller in comparison to δ . For the uniform description of the turbulent boundary layers, in the near wall region wall layer variables are introduced. In this description local reference to the length L_τ and the friction velocity u_τ in the y-direction are used [8]:

$$L_\tau = \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{\frac{\tau_W}{\rho_W}}}$$

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\tau_W}{\rho_W}}$$

Through these reference values, the dimensionless wall layer variables of the velocity u^+ and of the wall distance y^+ can be defined:

$$u^+ = \frac{\bar{u}}{u_\tau}$$

$$y^+ = \frac{y}{L_\tau} = \frac{y \cdot u_\tau}{\nu}$$

The velocity profile $\bar{u}(y)$ has a universal distribution in this dimensionless form:

$$u^+$$

If the dynamic eddy viscosity μ_t in the region $y^{+ \rightarrow 0}$ doesn't have a significant influence, the linear trend $u^{+}=y^{+}$ applies. The transition into the defect layer (Defektschicht) is described as an overlap region (Überlappungsbereich). This overlap region ($y^{+ \rightarrow \infty}$) is formulated via a logarithmic function u^{+} . This characteristic is also called logarithmic law of the wall and includes experimentally determined constants κ and C^+ . Figure 2 (right) shows the universal velocity profile close to the wall.

The illustrated logarithmic law of the wall (Figure 2) is used in the numerical calculation to obtain a solution, in case the solution up to the wall is not available. In this near-wall region the solution will be determined by a universal distribution. In this context the so-called wall functions are defined [3] [4] [8].

2.3.2.1 Wall Function (WF)

The standard Wall Function which is used in FLUENT, is based on the approach of Launder and Spalding. The law-of-the-wall for the mean velocity field is formulated as

$$u^{+} = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln$$

where for the dimensionless velocity u^{+} and the dimensionless wall distance y^{+} are defined as:

$$u^{+} \equiv \frac{u \cdot C_{\mu}^{\frac{1}{4}} \cdot k^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\frac{\tau_W}{\rho}}$$

$$y^{+} \equiv \frac{\rho \cdot C_{\mu}^{\frac{1}{4}} \cdot k^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot y}{\mu}$$

These formulations consist of the Karman's constant κ , an empirical constant E, the constant C_{μ} , the average fluid velocity u , the turbulent kinetic energy k , the wall distance y and the dynamic viscosity μ .

FLUENT uses the logarithmic law, when $y^{+} > 11.225$. If $y^{+} < 11.225$, the laminar stress-strain-relationship is applied [9]:

$$u^{+} = y^{+}$$

2.3.3 Heat Transfer Coefficient

The heat flux is computed taking into account both sides of a wall; the fluid and solid side. One description uses the heat flux to the wall from a fluid cell:

$$q = h_f(T_W - T_f) + q_{rad}$$

Here q is the fluid-side local heat transfer coefficient. This fluid-side heat transfer coefficient is calculated with the local flow-field conditions (e.g. turbulence, temperature, velocity, etc.). The temperature difference is calculated by the wall surface temperature T_W and the local fluid temperature T_f .

From the solid side, the heat flux is calculated using the thermal conductivity of the solid k_s , the local solid temperature T_s and the distance Δn between wall surface and the solid cell center:

$$q = \frac{k_s}{\Delta n} (T_w - T_s) + q_{rad}$$

With these two equations the boundary conditions at the wall can be calculated.

3. Geometry

For the simulation of the 3D moderator geometry the parts are defined as a Solid- and a Fluid-Domain (Figure 3). The complete geometry is simplified in ANSYS SpaceClaim. The simulations are separated into a Fluid- and a Solid-Simulation. Both simulation types are implemented with an energy deposition. The Solid-Domain of the moderator consists of AlMg3 and the Fluid-Domain defines the Deuterium.

Figure 3 Definition of the Solid- and the Fluid-Domain.

The moderator consists of an inlet of a AlMg3 tube with an entrance tube at the end; the liquid deuterium ($D_2(Liquid)$) flows in the chamber and fills it up to a certain level. The fluid level will be controlled by the pre- and back-pressure of the system. The liquid deuterium vaporizes by using the energy deposition. The energy deposition is deposited in the moderator chamber (AlMg3), in the Internal Vapour Chamber, and in the two phases of the deuterium ($D_2(Liquid)$ and $D_2(Vapour)$).

The vaporized deuterium ($D_2(Vapour)$) fills up the Internal Vapour Chamber. The rest of the vapour flows out through the Pipe with the Vapour Outlet-Holes (Figure 5) and then to the Outlet. In the system the vaporized deuterium will condensate under the pressure-temperature conditions of the liquid deuterium.

Figure 4 Simplified Moderator-Target: 3D-Geometry and detailed view of the 3D-Geometry.

Figure 5 Flow stream of the deuterium in the moderator (Blue: D_2 (Liquid) and Red: D_2 (Vapour)).

4. Mesh

The grid for the simulation is created by ANSYS Workbench with tetrahedron and hexahedron elements for the CFD-Mesher of Fluent. The CFD-Mesher use a linear option for the element order. This linear option removes midside nodes on all elements.

4.1 MESH OF THE SOLID-DOMAIN

The Solid-Domain are divided in 13 separated solids. The Solid-Domains are set to an Element Size from around $5.0e-004$ m to $1.0e-003$ m. For the modelling of the spatial discretization a growth rate of 1.2 for the Element Size is activated. For the solid body around 14 mio. Elements are created. The resolution at the inlet pipe is coarse, but for the simulation, this will be neglected, because this area is out of interest.

Figure 6 Mesh of the Solid-Domain of the AlMg3-Moderator Chamber

4.2 MESH OF THE FLUID-DOMAIN

The Fluid-Domain consists of 1 domain. The Fluid-Domain has a body resolution with an Element Size of around $2.0e-003$ m. From other simulation experience [10] it is known, that with this resolution a mesh independence is reached. The modelling of the spatial discretization use also a growth rate of 1.2 for the Element Size. For the Fluid-Domain around 21 mio. elements are created.

Figure 7 Definition of the Mesh Fluid-Domains of the moderator.

5. User Defined Function (UDF) for the Energy Deposition

The fits to the specific power density in the deuterium cold source calculated by MCNP6.1 is shown in Table 1 and the corresponding R^2 value is shown in Table 4. The form of the fitting equation is shown in Equation (5.4), and is a 3rd-order polynomial fit on the distance from a point SINQ z axis (the “source” point, which is also a fit parameter). The distance can be calculated as shown in Equation (5.3). The simulations were done with the standard double gaussian source definition and 590 MeV protons on SINQ target 13. The fits were performed on the cold source axis, i.e. -96° with respect to the SINQ x axis (as shown in Figure 8). The transformation from SINQ coordinates to cold source coordinates is shown in Equations (5.1)-(5.2) [11].

The cold source was segmented into 5418 individual volumes via a script then the total energy deposition induced by the proton beam was calculated using a F6+ tally. The segmentation was done using 20 edges between $x = [20; 60]$, 19 bins between $\phi = [0; 360]$, and 10 edges between $r^2 = [0; 15^2]$. Figure 9 shows the segmented geometry used in MCNP. Each volume of interest was segmented on this grid, then the non-real volumes were eliminated, yielding the final 5418 volumes [11].

*** All spatial dimensions are in cm.

Figure 8 SINQ coordinate systems. It can be seen that the cold source $[x]$ axis is -96 degrees from the SINQ x axis [1].

The energy depositions in the different parts of the deuterium cold source, have been calculated in MCNP6.1 by Ryan M. Bergmann and are implemented as User Defined Functions (UDFs). These UDFs include the functions for the energy deposition in x - and y -direction for the Zircalloy, the AlMg3 and the phases of deuterium ($D_{2Liquid}$, $D_{2Vapour}$). The following equations describe the energy deposition for the CFD simulation in the deuterium cold source [11].

$$x_{cs} = x \cdot \cos(\theta) + y \cdot \sin(\theta) \quad (5.1)$$

$$y_{cs} = -x \cdot \sin(\theta) + y \cdot \cos(\theta) \quad (5.2)$$

$$r = \sqrt{\|\vec{v} - \vec{z}_0\|^2} \quad (5.3)$$

$$q''' = a \cdot r^3 + b \cdot r^2 + c \cdot r + d \quad (5.4)$$

x is the position along the SINQ x axis and y is the position along the SINQ y axis. z is the position along the SINQ z axis in the beam direction. x_{sc} describes the coordinate parallel to the cold source axis, while y_{cs} describes the coordinate perpendicular to the cold source axis. θ defines the rotation angle between the cold source x axis and the SINQ x axis (-96°). With the position of interest in the cold source, the cold source coordinates are inserted with $\vec{v} = (x_{cs}, y_{cs}, z)$ and the “source” position with $\vec{z}_0 = (0, 0, \bar{z})$. q''' is the power density per mA proton beam intensity (W/g/mA) [11].

Figure 9 The segmented MCNP geometry [1].

5.1 ENERGY DEPOSITION OF ZIRCALLOY

Material	a	b	c	d	\bar{z}
Zircalloy	-2.4771E-06	3.3911E-04	-1.6212E-02	3.2414E-01	9.9549E+00

Table 1 3D fit parameter for Zircalloy

Figure 10 The 3D parameter fits for the Zircalloy materials in the liquid deuterium cold source [11].

$$q_{\text{Zircalloy}}''' = q''' \cdot \rho_{\text{Zircalloy}} \cdot 1000 \cdot I_{\text{current}} \quad (5.5)$$

The power has been adjusted to the correct beam current. In the MCNP6.1 simulations, the energy deposition is calculated as W/g/mA. Since the CFD models use the correct density of the Zircalloy, the calculation of the energy deposition in equation (5.5) must be corrected by the density in kg/m^3 . In order to correct the mass unit g, the energy deposition is additionally multiplied by 1000. Finally the energy deposition must be multiplied by the current I in mA.

The beam current is set as a parameter in the text user interface. The parameter with the name “current” is set to the value 1.5 (for example 1.5mA) and it provides the following input to Fluent’s command line interface:

(rp-var-define 'current 1.5 'real #f)

To read this parameter into the C-code UDF, the following code must be implemented in the UDF:

current_ma = RP_Get_Float("current");

```

1  /******
2  UDF for specifying steady-state Source Term for Cold Source for Target 13
3  *****/
4
5  #include "udf.h"
6  #include "math.h"
7
8
9  /* Definition from "Liquid Deuterium Cold Source Energy Deposition" by Ryan H. Bergmann is using the drawing definition from SINQ with a constant density of Liquid D2 */
10
11 DEFINE_PROFILE(s_rho_Zircalloy_Multiflash,t,i)
12 {
13     real xc[ND_ND]; /* this will hold the position vector */
14     double sF[double];
15     real x; /* x-coordinate parameter */
16     real y; /* y-coordinate parameter */
17     real z; /* z-coordinate parameter */
18     real r;
19     real rho = 0.035; /* Density of the Zircalloy in kg/m^3 */
20     real a = -0.0000024771; /* Parameter for Zircalloy */
21     real b = 0.00033911; /* Parameter for Zircalloy */
22     real c = -0.010212; /* Parameter for Zircalloy */
23     real d = 0.32414; /* Parameter for Zircalloy */
24     real zdach = 0.9540; /* Parameter for Zircalloy in cm */
25     real xcs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm */
26     real ycs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm */
27     real Phi = 95; /* Rotation angle between cold source x axis and SINQ x axis (-95) */
28     real PI = 3.141592;
29     real current_ma = RP_Get_Float("current"); /* Parameter in interface in mA */
30     face_t f; /* f = all the cell faces on the boundary */
31     begin_f_loop(f,t)
32     {
33         F_CENTROID(xc,f,t); /* the coordinates of the face centroid accessed by F_CENTROID */
34         x = xc[0]; /* The x coordinate stored in x[0] is assigned to variable x */
35         y = xc[1]; /* The y coordinate stored in x[1] is assigned to variable y */
36         z = xc[2]; /* The z coordinate stored in x[2] is assigned to variable z */
37         xcs = (x*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180)) + (y*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit function xco */
38         ycs = (x*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180)) + (y*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit function yco */
39         r = sqrt((pow((xcs-b),2)) + (pow((yco-d),2)) + (pow(((r*100)-zdach),2))); /* length of the vector vector-z0 */
40         F_PROFILE(f,t,i) = (a*(pow(r,3)) + b*(pow(r,2)) + c*r + d)*rho*1000*current_ma; /* The y coordinate is multiplied by 1000 for using the g as unit */
41     }
42     end_f_loop(f,t)
43 }

```

Figure 11 User Defined Function (UDF) for the energy deposition of Zircalloy

5.2 ENERGY DEPOSITION OF ALMG3

```

1  *****
2  UDF for specifying steady-state Source Term for Cold Source for Target II
3  *****
4
5  #include "udf.h"
6  #include "math.h"
7
8
9  /* Definition from "Liquid Deuterium Cold Source Energy Deposition" by Ryan M. Bergmann is using the drawing definition from SINQ with a constant density of Liquid D2*/
10
11 #DEFINE_PROFILE(c_dep_almg3_Phi111phase,t,i)
12 {
13     real xc[ND_ND]; /* this will hold the position vector */
14     double sF[double s];
15     real x; /* x-coordinate parameter*/
16     real y; /* y-coordinate parameter*/
17     real z; /* z-coordinate parameter*/
18     real r;
19     real rho = 2790; /* Density of the AlMg3 in kg/m^3*/
20     real a = -0.000021122; /* Parameter for AlMg3 */
21     real b = 0.00031419; /* Parameter for AlMg3 */
22     real c = -0.010105; /* Parameter for AlMg3 */
23     real d = 0.31898; /* Parameter for AlMg3 */
24     real zdash = 16.441; /* Parameter for AlMg3 in cm */
25     real xcxs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
26     real ycs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
27     real Phi=90; /* Rotation angle between cold source z axis and SINQ z axis (-90°)*/
28     real PI = 3.141592;
29     real current_ma = RP_Get_Float("current"); /* Parameter in Interface in mA */
30     face_t f; /* f = all the cell faces on the boundary*/
31     begin_f_loop(f,t)
32     {
33         #CENTROID(xc,f,t); /* the coordinates of the face centroid accessed by f_CENTROID */
34         s = xc[0]; /* The z coordinate stored in s[0] is assigned to variable x*/
35         y = xc[1]; /* The y coordinate stored in s[1] is assigned to variable y*/
36         z = xc[2]; /* The z coordinate stored in s[2] is assigned to variable z*/
37         xs=(s*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180))+(y*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit function xs*/
38         ycs=-(s*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180))+(y*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit function ycs*/
39         r=sqrt((pow((xcxs-0),2))+pow((ycs-0),2))+pow((z-dash),2)); /* length of the vector vector-xs */
40         F_PROFILE(f,t,i) =(a*(pow(r,3))+b*(pow(r,2))+c*r+d)*rho*1000*current_ma; /* The y coordinate is multiplied by 1000 for using the g as unit*/
41     }
42     end_f_loop(f,t)
43 }

```

Figure 12 User Defined Function (UDF) for the energy deposition of ALMG3

$$q_{ALMG3}''' = q''' \cdot \rho_{ALMG3} \cdot 1000 \cdot I_{current} \quad (5.6)$$

Material	a	b	c	d	\bar{z}
ALMG3	-2.1125E-06	3.1419E-04	-1.6105E-02	3.1898E-01	1.6441E+01

Table 2 3D fit parameter for ALMG3

Figure 13 The 3D parameter fits for the ALMg3 materials in the liquid deuterium cold source [11].

5.3 ENERGY DEPOSITION OF DEUTERIUM D_2

Material	a	b	c	d	\bar{z}
Liquid D_2	-1.0688E-05	1.6260E-03	-8.4387E-02	1.5481E-00	9.3477E+00
Vapour D_2	-5.7685E-06	9.2812E-04	-5.2480E-02	1.0937E-00	1.5892E+01

Table 3 3D fit parameter for deuterium D_2

$$q_{D_2,Liquid}''' = q''' \cdot \rho_{D_2,Liquid} \cdot 1000 \cdot I_{current} \quad (5.7)$$

$$q_{D_2,Vapour}''' = q''' \cdot \rho_{D_2,Vapour} \cdot 1000 \cdot I_{current} \quad (5.8)$$

Figure 14 The 3D parameter fits for the Liquid Deuterium materials in the Liquid Deuterium cold source [11].

Figure 15 The 3D parameter fits for the Vapour Deuterium materials in the Liquid Deuterium cold source [11].

```

1  | *****
2  | UDF for specifying steady-state Source Term for Cold Source for Target 13
3  | *****
4  |
5  | #include "udf.h"
6  | #include "math.h"
7  |
8  |
9  | /* Definition from "Liquid Deuterium Cold Source Energy Deposition" by Ryan M. Bergmann is using the drawing definition from SIMQ with a constant density of Liquid D2*/
10 |
11 | #DEFINE_PROFILE(c_dep_D2_Liquid_Multiphase,t,i)
12 | {
13 |     real xc[ND_ND]; /* this will hold the position vector */
14 |     double erf(double x);
15 |     real x; /* x-coordinate parameter*/
16 |     real y; /* y-coordinate parameter*/
17 |     real z; /* z-coordinate parameter*/
18 |     real r;
19 |     real rho = 162.4; /* Density of the Liquid D2 in kg/m^3*/
20 |     real a = -0.009810688; /* Parameter for liquid D2 */
21 |     real b = 0.0018280; /* Parameter for liquid D2 */
22 |     real c = -0.064387; /* Parameter for liquid D2 */
23 |     real d = 1.5581; /* Parameter for liquid D2 */
24 |     real zdash = 9.3477; /* Parameter for liquid D2 in cm */
25 |     real xcs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
26 |     real ycs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
27 |     real Phi=96; /* Rotation angle between cold source x axis and SIMQ x axis (-96)*/
28 |     real PI = 3.141592;
29 |     real current_ma = RP_Get_Float("current"); /* Parameter in Interface in mA */
30 |     face_t f; /* f = all the cell faces on the boundary*/
31 |     begin_f_loop(f,t)
32 |     {
33 |         F_CENTROID(xc,f,t); /* the coordinates of the face centroid accessed by F_CENTROID */
34 |         x = xc[0]; /* The x coordinate stored in x[0] is assigned to variable x*/
35 |         y = xc[1]; /* The y coordinate stored in x[1] is assigned to variable y*/
36 |         z = xc[2]; /* The z coordinate stored in x[2] is assigned to variable z*/
37 |         xcs=(x*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180))+(y*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit Function xcs*/
38 |         ycs=(x*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180))-(y*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit Function ycs*/
39 |         r=sqrt((pow((xcs-0),2))+pow((ycs-0),2))+pow(((z*100)-zdash),2)); /* Length of the Vector vector-to-z */
40 |         F_PROFILE(f,t,i) =(a*(pow(r,3))+b*(pow(r,2))+c*r+d)*rho*1000*current_ma; /* The y coordinate is multiplied by 1000 for using the g as unit*/
41 |     }
42 |     end_f_loop(f,t)
43 | }

```

Figure 16 User Defined Function (UDF) for the energy deposition of Deuterium Liquid

```

1  | *****
2  | UDF for specifying steady-state Source Term for Cold source for Target 13
3  | *****
4  |
5  | #include "udf.h"
6  | #include "math.h"
7  |
8  |
9  | /* Definition from "Liquid Deuterium Cold Source Energy Deposition" by Ryan M. Bergmann is using the drawing definition from SIMQ with a constant density of Liquid D2*/
10 |
11 | #DEFINE_PROFILE(c_dep_D2_Vapour_Multiphase,t,i)
12 | {
13 |     real xc[ND_ND]; /* this will hold the position vector */
14 |     double erf(double x);
15 |     real x; /* x-coordinate parameter*/
16 |     real y; /* y-coordinate parameter*/
17 |     real z; /* z-coordinate parameter*/
18 |     real r;
19 |     real rho = 0.1680; /* Density of the Vapour D2 in kg/m^3*/
20 |     real a = -0.0000057885; /* Parameter for Vapour D2 */
21 |     real b = 0.00092812; /* Parameter for Vapour D2 */
22 |     real c = -0.85248; /* Parameter for Vapour D2 */
23 |     real d = 1.00370; /* Parameter for Vapour D2 */
24 |     real zdash = 15.8920; /* Parameter for Vapour D2 in cm */
25 |     real xcs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
26 |     real ycs; /* Position parallel to cold source axis in cm*/
27 |     real Phi=96; /* Rotation angle between cold source z axis and SIMQ x axis (-96)*/
28 |     real PI = 3.141592;
29 |     real current_ma = RP_Get_Float("current"); /* Parameter in Interface in mA */
30 |     face_t f; /* f = all the cell faces on the boundary*/
31 |     begin_f_loop(f,t)
32 |     {
33 |         F_CENTROID(xc,f,t); /* the coordinates of the face centroid accessed by F_CENTROID */
34 |         x = xc[0]; /* The x coordinate stored in x[0] is assigned to variable x*/
35 |         y = xc[1]; /* The y coordinate stored in x[1] is assigned to variable y*/
36 |         z = xc[2]; /* The z coordinate stored in x[2] is assigned to variable z*/
37 |         xcs=(x*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180))+(y*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit Function xcs*/
38 |         ycs=(x*100)*sin(Phi*(PI/180))-(y*100)*cos(Phi*(PI/180)); /*Fit Function ycs*/
39 |         r=sqrt((pow((xcs-0),2))+pow((ycs-0),2))+pow(((z*100)-zdash),2)); /* Length of the Vector vector-to-z */
40 |         F_PROFILE(f,t,i) =(a*(pow(r,3))+b*(pow(r,2))+c*r+d)*rho*1000*current_ma; /* The y coordinate is multiplied by 1000 for using the g as unit*/
41 |     }
42 |     end_f_loop(f,t)
43 | }

```

Figure 17 User Defined Function (UDF) for the energy deposition of Deuterium Vapour

5.4 COLD SOURCE MATERIAL SPECIFIC POWER DENSITY FITS

The fit parameters are calculated with the determination R^2 . The 3D fit coefficient of the determination R^2 are shown in the Table 4.

Material	R^2
Zircalloy	9.2598E-01
AlMg3	8.4638E-01
Liquid D_2	9.8601E-01
Vapour D_2	9.7693E-01

Table 4 3D fit coefficient of determination R^2

Figure 18 The distance dependence of the specific power density for the cold source materials [11].

6. Material data

6.1 PHASE DIAGRAM OF DEUTERIUM

The phase diagram with the three variables pressure, temperature, and volume is shown schematically in Figure 19. The surfaces are of two kinds: the solid and the fluid. The solid consists of arrayed molecules, the internal energy of which is a function of pressure. The fluid is a randomly ordered molecular phase, the internal energy of which is a function of temperature. The fluid can be defined as different parts: fluid (meaning just high pressure), liquid, gas, vapor (gas near or on the liquid line), high vacuum, and the plasma (ionized gas) [12].

The curve b-c defines the saturation curve on the vapor side. On the other side one can find the liquid curve a-c. More generally, the saturation curve is the line g-d-a-c-b-h. But there are always two sides in equilibrium at constant temperature: g-d-a-c and h-b-c. The solid is g-d and its vapour h-b. The liquid is a-c and its vapour b-c. The liquid and vapor become a single phase at the critical point c. The triple "line" is made up of point d (solid), point a (liquid), and b (vapor). This is the only place where three phases are in equilibrium with each other. (In the simpler pressure-temperature phase diagram, the triple "line" collapses to the more familiar triple "point") [12].

This chapter deals with the properties of the liquid and the vapour phase above the solid. These vapour pressures are called "saturated".

Figure 19 Pressure-temperature-volume diagram for a pure-component [13].

There are two important fixed points: the triple point and the critical point. The triple point is the single pressure and temperature at which the solid, liquid, and vapour phases are all in equilibrium. It is an important fixed point for use because pass through it, the Deuterium liquefy and freeze there. In case of the moderator, it is not allowed to pass through this curve because the freezing would compromise the safety of the shroud.

McConville and Peaves are determined for the triple-point temperatures of deuterium of 18.73 K [14] at an the estimated pressures 17 150 Pa [12].

Another important point is the critical point, where liquid and vapour merge into a single fluid phase and the internal translational energy is zero. This is usually considered the most important fixed point. The critical point values are the critical temperature of 38.34 K and a pressure of 1665000 Pa (16.65 bar), for deuterium.

The area of operation for the moderator is between these two fixed points.

Projections of the P-v-T 3D surface

Figure 20 Projection of the pressure-temperature diagram (left) and pressure-volume diagram (right) [13].

6.1.1 Pressure of Deuterium

The vapour pressure curve indicates the temperature at which a substance evaporates under a given pressure or how far the pressure of a liquid has to be reduced at a given temperature in order for the evaporation to begin. The pressure and temperature values that are linked by the vapour pressure

curve apply to evaporation and liquefaction [15]. The values for the vapour pressure curve from the liquid-side and the vapour-side are set in the Table 5 and visualized in

Figure 21 Vapour-pressure-curve of deuterium with the critical and triple point [16] [12].

	Temperature T	Pressure p (Liquid-Side) (Air Liquide [16])	Pressure p (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
	<i>K</i>	-	-
	4,2		5E-14
	6		2E-09
	8		0,0000012
	10		0,000065
	12		0,00098
	14		0,0073
	16		0,0339
	18		0,116

REPORT ON THE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE AND TECHNICAL LAYOUT OF EFFICIENT MODERATOR ASSEMBLIES

Deliverable: D4.4

Date: 26/03/2021

Triple Point	18,71	0,1707	
	18,73		0,172
	19,15	0,2355	
	19,65	0,2896	
	20		0,293
	20,15	0,3526	
	20,65	0,4253	
	21,15	0,508	
	21,65	0,6037	
	22		0,605
	22,15	0,711	
	22,65	0,8320	
	23,15	0,9670	
	23,65	1,117	
	24		1,12
	24,15	1,284	
	24,65	1,467	
	25,15	1,668	
	25,65	1,889	
	26		1,89
	26,15	2,129	
	26,65	2,390	
	27,15	2,674	
	27,65	2,980	
	28		2,99
	28,15	3,311	
	28,65	3,668	
	29,15	4,051	
	29,65	4,462	
	30		4,5
	30,15	4,903	
	30,65	5,374	
31,15	5,878		
31,65	6,416		
32		6,49	
32,15	6,990		
32,65	7,599		

	33,15	8,246	
	33,65	8,931	
	34		9,02
	34,15	9,653	
	34,65	10,41	
	35		10,5
	35,15	11,20	
	35,65	12,03	
	36,15	12,88	
	36,65	13,76	
	37,15	14,66	
	37,65	15,51	
Critical Point	38,34	16,65	

Table 5 Values of the vapour-pressure-curve of Deuterium [12] [16]

6.1.2 Density of Deuterium

With the definition of the specific volume

$$v = \frac{1}{\rho}$$

the influence of the density can be introduced into the phase-diagram. In thermodynamics the pressure-volume diagram is normally used. A pressure-volume diagram can be used to distinguish between boiling and dew line. The values of the area of operation of the moderator are shown in Table 6. The pressure-density diagram (respectively the pressure-volume diagram) of deuterium with their boiling and dew line is shown Figure 22.

Figure 22 Pressure-density-diagram of deuterium.

The area of operation of the deuterium moderator is in a small range between 18.11 K and 38.34 K. In this area the liquid deuterium can evaporate to its vapour phase. Above this critical point of 39.34 K the deuterium becomes suddenly vapour. Under the 18.11 K there is a complete liquid phase. In order to reach this operation area the moderator chamber must be operated in a small temperature range. Close to the 18.11 K only a small amount of Deuterium evaporates. At the opposite side close to the 38.34 K a big amount of Deuterium evaporates. The best way to operate the moderator is to set a working temperature in a range between these two values.

	Temperature T	Density ρ (Liquid-Side) (Air Liquide [16])	Density ρ (Vapour-Side) (Air Liquide [16])	Density ρ (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Density ρ (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
	<i>K</i>	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$
	4,2			5E-14	7,25E-13
	6			2E-09	1,81E-08
	8			0,0000012	8,06E-06
	10			0,000065	3,26E-04
	12			0,00098	4,03E-03

**REPORT ON THE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE
AND TECHNICAL LAYOUT OF EFFICIENT
MODERATOR ASSEMBLIES**

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Triple Point	14			0,0073	0,03
	16			0,0339	0,10
	18			0,116	0,32
	18,71	174,724	0,4956		
	18.73			0,172	0,46
	19,15	173,788	0,5859		
	19,65	172,718	0,7022		
	20			171,48	0,73
	20,15	171,625	0,8342		
	20,65	170,499	0,9829		
	21,15	169,333	1,1496		
	21,65	168,124	1,3355		
	22			167,37	1,41
	22,15	166,873	1,5416		
	22,65	165,583	1,7694		
	23,15	164,262	2,0201		
	23,65	162,916	2,2952		
	24			162,86	2,44
	24,15	161,551	2,5963		
	24,65	160,174	2,9250		
	25,15	158,787	3,2834		
	25,65	157,391	3,6735		
	26			157,83	3,96
	26,15	155,986	4,0978		
	26,65	154,569	4,5592		
	27,15	153,135	5,0607		
	27,65	151,680	5,6061		
	28			152,19	6,12
	28,15	150,196	6,1997		
	28,65	148,677	6,8463		
	29,15	147,114	7,5517		
	29,65	145,496	8,3225		
30			145,66	9,14	
30,15	143,813	9,1662			
30,65	142,051	10,0914			
31,15	140,194	11,1074			

Critical Point	31,65	138,226	12,2239		
	32			137,89	13,33
	32,15	136,125	13,4502		
	32,65	133,869	14,7938		
	33,15	131,435	16,2584		
	33,65	128,802	17,8419		
	34			128,34	19,34
	34,15	125,955	19,5358		
	34,65	122,886	21,3261		
	35			122,70	23,44
	35,15	119,596	23,1976		
	35,65	116,070	25,1393		
	36,15	112,228	27,1495		
	36,65	107,793	29,2380		
	37,15	101,206	31,4209		
	37,65	76,105	33,3058		
	38,34	69,797	69,7966		

Table 6 Values of boiling and dew line e of deuterium [12] [16].

6.1.3 Viscosity of Deuterium

Viscosity describes the toughness of liquids and gases (fluids) [17] [18]. A distinction is made between the dynamic and the kinematic viscosity. The dynamic viscosity μ is defined as the ratio of shear stress and velocity gradient perpendicular to the direction of flow. This is called Newton's law of friction. The kinematic viscosity ν results from the dynamic viscosity through the density ρ .

$$\nu = \frac{\mu}{\rho}$$

The viscosity diagram of deuterium is shown the Figure 23.

Figure 23 Viscosity of deuterium [12]

	Temperature T	Viscosity μ (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Viscosity μ (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
	K	$Pa \cdot s$	$Pa \cdot s$
Triple Point	4,2		0,00000016
	10		0,00000057
	15		0,0000009
	18,71		
	18.73		
	20	0,0000391	0,0000013
	22	0,0000331	
	24	0,0000288	
	25		0,0000017
	26	0,0000255	
Critical Point	28	0,000023	
	30	0,0000208	0,000002
	32	0,0000179	
	34	0,0000158	
	36	0,0000138	
	38,34		
	40		0,0000027
	60		0,0000039
	77,4		0,0000049

Table 7 Values of viscosity of deuterium [12]

6.1.4 Heat Capacity of Deuterium

The specific heat capacity describes the ability of a substance to store thermal energy. The values of the specific heat capacity are shown in Table 8, the Figure 24 and Figure 25.

Figure 24 Specific heat capacity of deuterium from 0 to 160 kJ/kgK

Figure 25 Specific heat capacity of deuterium from 0 to 20 kJ/kgK

	Temperature T	Specific heat capacity c_p (Liquid-Side) (Richardson et al. [19])	Specific heat capacity c_p (Vapour-Side) (Richardson et al. [19])	Specific heat capacity c_p (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Specific heat capacity c_p (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
	K	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$
Triple Point	18,724	5627	5364		
	18.73				

	19	5674	5383		
	20	5852	5464	5709,74	
	21	6044	5563		
	22	6252	5683	5957,99	
	23	6477	5826		
	23,661	6638	5935		
	24	6724	5996	6454,49	
	25	6996	6197		
	26	7298	6436	7199,24	
	27	7640	6722		
	28	8031	7067	7943,99	
	29	8489	7488		
	30	9036	8013	8936,99	
	31	9712	8681		
	32	10576	9562	10426,48	
	33	11741	10775		
	34	13421	12555	12164,23	
	35	12103	15430	13405,48	
	36	21143	20869		
	37	34179	34920		
	38	132060	137920		
Critical Point	38,34				

Table 8 Specific heat capacity of deuterium [12] [19].

6.1.5 Thermal Conductivity of Deuterium

Thermal conductivity is a material property that determines the flow of heat through a material based on thermal conduction. The thermal conductivity shows how well a material conducts heat or how well it is suitable for thermal insulation [17] [18].

The thermal conductivity of most materials increases slightly with increasing temperature. At a phase transition or state transition (e.g. solid ↔ liquid ↔ gaseous), however, the conductivity usually changes sharply and suddenly.

Figure 26 Thermal conductivity of deuterium [12] [20]

	Temperature T	Thermal Conductivity λ (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Thermal Conductivity λ (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Thermal Conductivity λ (Liquide- Side) (She et al. [20])	Thermal Conductivity λ (Vapour-Side) (She et al. [20])
	K	$\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$	$\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$	$\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$	$\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$
Triple Point	4,2		0,001		
	10		0,004		
	15		0,007		
	18.73				
	20	0,1	0,01		
	24,3			0,135	
	24,9				0,0137
Critical Point	25	0,11	0,013		
	30	0,1	0,015		
	35	0,09			
	38,34				
	40			0,021	
	60			0,036	
	77,4			0,047	

Table 9 Values of thermal conductivity of deuterium [12] [20]

6.1.6 Thermal Expansion of Deuterium

Thermal expansion describe the change in the geometric dimensions (length, surface area, volume) of a body, caused by a change in its temperature. Schwalbe et al. [21] measured the thermal expansion and described this with the following formula.

$$\alpha(p, T) = b_1 + 2 \cdot b_2 \cdot (T - T_{tp}) + 3 \cdot b_3 \cdot (T - T_{tp})^2 - \beta(p, T) \cdot [c_1 + 2 \cdot c_2 \cdot (T - T_{tp})]$$

with

$$\beta(p, T) = \frac{a}{p + p_0(T)}$$

and

$$p_0(T) = c_0 + c_1 \cdot (T - T_{tp}) + c_2 \cdot (T - T_{tp})^2$$

The coefficients for the calculation of the thermal expansion are shown in Table 10.

	Coefficients (Schwalbe et al. [21])
<i>a</i>	0,12
<i>b</i> ₁	0,0017
<i>b</i> ₂	0,00028
<i>b</i> ₃	0,00001
<i>c</i> ₀	152,0
<i>c</i> ₁	-13,2
<i>c</i> ₂	0,50
<i>p</i>	4,44

Table 10 Coefficients of the thermal expansion [21]

Figure 27 Thermal expansion of deuterium [21]

	Temperature T	$p_0(T)$	$\beta(p, T)$	Thermal Expansion $\alpha(p, T)$ (Liquid-Side) (Schwalbe et al. [21])
Triple Point	K			$\frac{1}{K}$
	18.73			
	18,7	152,088462	0,00076663	0,01181838
	18,8	150,772792	0,00077313	0,01183631
	18,9	149,467122	0,00077969	0,01185484
	19	148,171452	0,00078631	0,01187397
	19,1	146,885782	0,00079299	0,0118937
	19,2	145,610112	0,00079973	0,01191402
	19,3	144,344442	0,00080654	0,01193495
	19,4	143,088772	0,0008134	0,01195648
	19,5	141,843102	0,00082033	0,01197861
	19,6	140,607432	0,00082732	0,01200134
	19,7	139,381762	0,00083437	0,01202466
	19,8	138,166092	0,00084148	0,01204859
	19,9	136,960422	0,00084865	0,01207312
20	135,764752	0,00085589	0,01209825	
20,1	134,579082	0,00086319	0,01212398	

	20,2	133,403412	0,00087055	0,0121503
	20,3	132,237742	0,00087798	0,01217723
	20,4	131,082072	0,00088546	0,01220476
	20,5	129,936402	0,00089301	0,01223289
	20,6	128,800732	0,00090063	0,01226162
	20,7	127,675062	0,0009083	0,01229095
	20,8	126,559392	0,00091603	0,01232087
	20,9	125,453722	0,00092383	0,0123514
	21	124,358052	0,00093169	0,01238253
Critical Point	38,34			

Table 11 Values of thermal expansion of deuterium [21]

6.1.7 Speed of Sound of Deuterium

Also give Souers et al. [12] and Richardson et al. [19] the description of the speed of sound for Deuterium.

Figure 28 Speed of Sound [12] [19]

	Temperature T	Speed of Sound c_s (Liquid-Side) (Richardson et al. [19])	Speed of Sound c_s (Vapour-Side) (Richardson et al. [19])	Speed of Sound c_s (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Speed of Sound c_s (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
	K	$\frac{m}{s}$	$\frac{m}{s}$	$\frac{m}{s}$	$\frac{m}{s}$
	18,724	1085,5	250,95		

Triple Point	18.73				
	19	1079,8	252,53		
	20	1058,6	257,98	1060	
	21	1036,6	262,99		
	22	1013,6	267,56	1010	
	23	989,48	271,68		
	23,661	972,85	274,17		
	24	964,09	275,37	961	
	25	937,27	278,61		
	26	908,93	281,4	907	
	27	878,92	283,75		
	28	847,14	285,66	846	
	29	813,47	287,11		
	30	777,76	288,11	778	
	31	739,87	288,66		
	32	699,6	288,75	694	
	33	656,7	288,42		
34	610,82	287,72			
35	561,44	286,83			
36	507,68	286,2			
Critical Point	37	447,068	287,25		
	38	374,12	297,24		
	38,34				

Table 12 Values of the Speed of Sound [12] [19]

6.1.8 Surface Tension

The surface tension of liquid deuterium σ varies as a power law of the temperature:

$$\sigma(T) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \sigma_i \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_c}\right)^{n_i}$$

Where the critical temperature for Deuterium is $T_c = 38.34K$. The literature Mulero et al. [22] provides the following coefficients:

$$k = 1 \sigma_0 = 0.009376N.m^{-1} n_0 = 1.258$$

Note that the coefficients differ significantly from the REFPROP version 9.0 (TPFS is based on REFPROP version 7) [22] for which we have:

$$k = 1\sigma_0 = 0.00795N.m^{-1}n_0 = 1$$

The value for σ_0 is not directly available in the references cited here, so we determined it by fitting the saturation data given in the TPFS database with the surface tension correlation using σ_0 as the only free parameter.

	Temperature T	Surface Tension σ (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Surface Tension σ (Liquid-Side) (Mulero et al. [22])	Surface Tension σ (Liquid-Side) (REFPROP [22])
	K	$\frac{J}{m^2}$	$\frac{N}{m}$	$\frac{N}{m}$
Triple Point	18.73	0,00382	0,00403541	0,00406748
	20	0,00356	0,003708	0,0038029
	22	0,00314	0,00320667	0,00338818
	24	0,00271	0,00272096	0,00297347
	26	0,00228	0,00225246	0,00255876
	28	0,00185	0,00180323	0,00214405
	30	0,00142	0,00137597	0,00172934
	32	0,00101	0,00097457	0,00131463
	34	0,000621	0,00060499	0,00089992
	35	0,000441	0,00043517	0,00069257
	36	0,000274	0,00027814	0,00048521
	37	0,000133	0,00013794	0,00027786
Critical Point	38,34			

Table 13 Values of the Surface Tension of Deuterium [12] [22]

There is an overview of the fits on the following Figure 29:

Figure 29 Surface Tension of Deuterium [12] [22]

6.1.9 Enthalpy

6.1.9.1 Standard State Enthalpy

For the Standard State Enthalpy it is important to understand the unit that ANSYS used. The unit $J/kgmol$ does mean that it used $k \cdot gmol$. The SI units used refer to Chemistry.

The latent heat must be multiplied by the molecular weight and the factor of 1000.

Equivalent: $1 \text{ kJ/mol} = 1 \text{ kJ/gmol} = 1000 \text{ kJ/kgmol}$.

Chase et al. [23] define the enthalpy of formation of gas at standard conditions.

	Standard State Enthalpy $\Delta_f H_{gas}^\circ$ (Liquid-Side)	Standard State Enthalpy $\Delta_f H_{gas}^\circ$ (Vapour-Side) (Chase et al. [23])
	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$
		221,72

Table 14 Standard State Enthalpy $\Delta_f H_{gas}^\circ$ of deuterium [23]

6.1.9.2 Total Enthalpy

Souers et al. [12] measured the total enthalpy of the deuterium (Table 15). So the liquid curve in the Figure 30 shows the step at the formation at the triple and the critical point.

Figure 30 Total Entalpy of deuterium [12]

	Temperature T	Total Enthalpy H (Liquide-Side) (Souers et al. [12])	Total Enthalpy H (Vapour-Side) (Souers et al. [12])
Triple Point	<i>K</i>	$\frac{J}{mol}$	$\frac{J}{mol}$
	4,2	3	87
	6	5	125
	8	7	166
	10	9	208
	12	14	249
	14	23	291
	16	37	333
	18	56	374
	18.73	264	384
	20	280	400
	22	330	430
	24	390	460
	26	460	480
	28	525	495
	30	600	500
32	680	490	
34	765	455	
35	810	420	

Critical Point	36	870	390
	37	930	350
	38,34	1257	107

Table 15 Total Enthalpy H of deuterium [12]

6.2 MATERIAL DATA OF ALMG3

AlMg3 is an aluminum alloy referenced as 5754 Aluminum [24].

Temperature	Density ρ	Specific Heat Capacity c_p	Thermal Conductivity λ	Dynamic Viscosity η
(K)	$\left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)$	$\left(\frac{J}{kgK}\right)$	$\left(\frac{W}{mK}\right)$	$\left(\frac{kg}{m \cdot s}\right)$
293.15	2700	900	130	

Table 16 Material data of AlMg3 [24]

6.3 MATERIAL DATA OF ZIRCALLOY

The material data of Zircalloy is described in Table 17.

Temperature	Density ρ	Specific Heat Capacity c_p	Thermal Conductivity λ	Dynamic Viscosity η
(K)	$\left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)$	$\left(\frac{J}{kgK}\right)$	$\left(\frac{W}{mK}\right)$	$\left(\frac{kg}{m \cdot s}\right)$
293.15	6635.62	285.67856	13.37955	
298.15	6634.69	286.19056	13.40338	
300.15	6634.32	286.39536	13.41305	
333.15	6628.20	289.77456	13.58282	
373.15	6620.78	293.87056	13.81483	
413.15	6613.36	297.96656	14.07559	
423.15	6611.51	298.99056	14.14527	
453.15	6605.94	302.06256	14.36509	
493.15	6598.52	306.15856	14.68333	
533.15	6591.10	310.25456	15.03031	
573.15	6583.68	314.35056	15.40603	
613.15	6576.26	318.44656	15.81050	
653.15	6568.84	322.54256	16.24371	
693.15	6561.42	326.63856	16.70565	
733.15	6554.00	330.73456	17.19635	
773.15	6546.58	334.83056	17.71578	
813.15	6539.16	338.92656	18.26395	
853.15	6531.74	343.02256	18.84087	
873.15	6528.03	345.07056	19.14010	

893.15	6524.32	347.11856	19.44652	
933.15	6516.90	351.21456	20.08092	
973.15	6509.48	355.31056	20.74406	
1013.15	6502.06	359.40656	21.43595	
1053.15	6494.64	363.50256	22.15657	
1083	6489.10	366.5592	22.71307	

Table 17 Material data of Zircalloy-II [25] [26]

7. Results

The simulations have been divided into a simulation with a fluid-domain of the deuterium and the solid-domain of the AlMg-3 moderator chamber. The simulations use the k - ϵ -turbulence model with the near wall formulation of the Wall Function (WF).

7.1 TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION IN THE DEUTERIUM

In order to understand the evaporation of the deuterium under the given boundary conditions, several simulations were carried out. The energy deposition from the Monte Carlo simulations from Chapter 5.3 with a beam current of 1.5 mA for the SINQ target was used. This is the currently maximum beam current at the SINQ target. The simulation use the pressure inlet conditions for the operation point. For this pressure inlet a temperature of 20 K at around $1 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ is used. For the pressure outlet conditions the approach of 25 K is used. In the first simulation for the operation point the walls will be defined as adiabatic conditions.

Figure 31 Description of the Energy deposition of the Monte-Carlo-Simulation (left) and the implementation in the CFD-simulation (right)

The Figure 31 shows the definition of the spatially resolved energy deposition from the Monte-Carlos simulations as well as the implementation in the CFD simulation. Due to the different coordinate systems, a coordinate transformation was carried out by describing the energy deposition in the User Defined Functions (UDFs). As already explained in Chapter 5.3, there is a description for both the liquid and the gas phase of deuterium.

Figure 32 Energy deposition in the liquid and vapour deuterium at 1.5 mA at SINQ target (with liquid density $162,4.kg/m^3$ and vapour density $0.168.kg/m^3$)

The approach of this investigation is to determine the temperature of the deuterium. In the current-dependent description of the energy deposition of the deuterium, it is assumed that a beam current of 1.5 mA is established at the SINQ target. Figure 32 shows the energy deposition of the liquid and vapour deuterium used over the radius of the SINQ target. The density of liquid deuterium at this temperature is $162.4 kg/m^3$ and that of vapour deuterium $0.168 kg/m^3$.

Figure 33 shows the visualisation surfaces and the measuring lines in the vapour chamber and the outlet. In the measuring lines the temperature distribution and the absolute pressure are measured.

Figure 33 Visualisation Surfaces and Measuring Lines in the vapour chamber and the outlet.

Figure 34 shows the temperature and absolute pressure field at the operation area. The temperature range is between 20K and 25.2K. The temperatures in the various positions of the moderator can be clearly seen. Temperatures between 20 K and 21 K can be seen in the vapour chamber. Temperatures of approx. 25 K can be seen in the area of the outlet. If it is also a viewing at the absolute pressure, it can determine an average temperature with the associated absolute pressure.

At this point it should be noted that the fluid is viewed as a single phase and the temperature and the absolute pressure are examined at which a phase change occurs.

Figure 34 Comparison of the simulation with the UDF of the energy deposition of the deuterium at 1.5 mA at SINQ target. Left the temperature of the deuterium, right the absolute pressure of the deuterium.

To understand which phase area exist, the temperature and the absolute pressure have been determined using measuring lines in the vapor chamber and the outlet (Figure 33). Figure 35 represents the temperature distribution and the absolute pressure in the measuring line in the vapour chamber. These values were then averaged over this measuring line. The average temperature is around 20.7 K at an average absolute pressure of 101328 Pa.

Figure 35 Temperature and absolute pressure of the deuterium in the measuring line in the vapour chamber

In the same way Figure 36 shows the temperature distribution and the absolute pressure in the measuring line in the outlet. These values were then also averaged over this measuring line. The average temperature is around 24.96 K at an average absolute pressure of 101328 Pa.

Figure 36 Temperature and absolute pressure of the deuterium in the measuring line in the outlet

When the averaged values from the Internal Vapour Chamber and the Outlet are entered in a p-T diagram of the deuterium (Figure 37), it can determine the present phase. The two points show that the point in the Internal Vapour Chamber lies in the liquid phase and the point in the Outlet in the vapour phase. This means also that the energy input to the fluid phase in the vapour chamber is too low to vaporize the deuterium.

Figure 37 Operation Points in the p-T-diagram for the Internal Vapour Chamber and the Outlet

At this point the question arises whether enough energy can be supplied via the AlMg3 moderator chamber to move the point in the Internal Vapor Chamber into the vapour phase area. As already shown in the simulation, the energy of the deuterium at 1.5 mA on the SINQ target is not enough on its own.

In order to allow the deuterium to evaporate, the walls set to temperatures of 273 K and 473 K. The simulations (Figure 38) show that an increase in the wall temperature causes the desired rise in temperature in the Deuterium.

Figure 38 Comparison of the behaviour by increasing the wall temperature of the moderator.

If the results are also averaged on the measurement lines in the Internal Vapour Chamber and entered into the p-T diagram (Figure 39), the shift into the vapour area can be clearly seen.

Figure 39 Operation Points in the p-T-diagram for the vapour chamber at different wall temperatures

For a better illustration of how far the temperature lies within the permissible limits between the triple and the critical point, the deuterium temperatures have been plotted against the wall temperatures (Figure 40). With this order, the wall temperatures can be better assessed.

Figure 40 Deuterium-temperature versus wall-temperature

7.2 TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION IN THE MODERATOR CHAMBER

As already mentioned in the previous chapter, the question arises whether the energy input via the AlMg3 moderator chamber is sufficient to evaporate the deuterium in the Internal Vapour Chamber. In the simulations, the assumption was done, that the operation range lies between 18.71 K and 38.34 K. The walls in contact with the liquid phase were exposed to 18.71 K, while the walls in contact with the vapour phase were exposed to 38.34 K. In order to determine the temperature within the moderator chamber, different volumetric heat power from 200000 W/m^3 up to 2000000000 W/m^3 were induced. Figure 41 show the orientation of the moderator chamber.

Figure 41 Orientation of the moderator chamber and the orientation of the simulations

In Figure 42 and Figure 43, only the lower shell of the AlMg3-moderator chamber has been visualized. The temperatures in the AlMg3 moderator chamber at different volumetric heat power can be seen in the Figure 42 from 0 to 20000000 W/m^3 . The range up to 200000000 W/m^3 can be seen analogously in Figure 43.

Figure 42 Simulation of the solid-domain of the AlMg3-Moderator chamber with different volumetric heat power up to 20000000 W/m^3

Figure 43 Simulation of the solid-domain of the AlMg3-Moderator chamber with different volumetric heat power up to 2000000000 W/m^3

In order to obtain a prediction about the defined volumetric heat power and the energy deposition determined from the Monte-Carlo simulations were compared with each other (Figure 44). The energy deposition of the Monte-Carlo simulations with different beam currents at the SINQ target was determined. The comparison shows that the volumetric heat power used with the different energy deposition can only be achieved with very high beam currents at the SINQ target. However, since a maximum beam current of approximately 1.5 mA is possible at the SINQ target, it can be easily deduced from this, that the energy supplied to the moderator is not sufficient to realize the evaporation by means of heat power of the AlMg3-moderator chamber. The corresponding volumetric heat power to the energy deposition of the Monte-Carlo simulation at 1.5 mA can be seen at 2000000 W/m^3 .

Figure 44 Comparison of the Energy deposition of the Monte-Carlo-Simulation and the three volumetric heat power

The solid temperature at the bottom of the moderator was measured for the different volumetric heat power. This temperature was set to the diagram in Figure 45 and analytically determined the Deuterium temperature in the Internal Vapour Chamber.

The fluid temperature in the Internal Vapour Chamber (Figure 3) of the moderator was determined from the fluid simulations of the deuterium and a linear temperature function was worked out. This linear temperature function is shown in Figure 46 as “Averaged Deuterium-Temperature in vapour chamber”. The prevailing fluid temperature can be determined through this relationship between the solid temperature (wall temperature) and the linear temperature function “Averaged Deuterium-Temperature in vapour chamber”.

Figure 45 Relation of the Deuterium-temperature and the wall temperature of the AlMg3-Moderator chamber.

Figure 46 Operation area and the different areas of the phases

Figure 45 shows that the deuterium temperatures for the different volumetric heat power are within the moderator's operating range. The overview of the energy deposition of the different parts (Figure

47) shows that there is a difference in the energy deposition at different positions over the radius. Around the position of the vapour chamber box from around 32 cm to 44 cm the energy deposition lies for AlMg3 at around 200000 W/m^3 .

Figure 47 Energy deposition for the different material parts of the cold source moderator.

Under the approach that the absolute pressure doesn't change, the calculated deuterium temperature can be marked in the p-T-diagram. The Figure 48 show that the calculated Deuterium temperature in the Internal Vapour Chamber lies close to the vapour curve. This means that the energy deposition of the AlMg3-moderator chamber reaches at 1.5 mA the level for the phase change. But in Figure 47 is shown that this energy deposition lies always under the necessary energy deposition for a phase change. When the beam current at SINQ is also not close to 1.5 mA it can be expected that the energy deposition is not large enough for the phase change in the deuterium.

Figure 48 Operation Points in the p-T-diagram for the vapour chamber at different wall temperatures of different volumetric heat power

8. Options for effective moderation

The CFD-simulation for the current Cold Source moderator shows, that it is difficult to handle the phase change from liquid to vapour deuterium in a small range. The simulation prognosticates that the REH under the current conditions will not be filled with the vapour D_2 but still with liquid. However, this transition is necessary to increase the effectiveness of the moderator respectively the target station.

Figure 49 A horizontal slice through the MCNP simulation geometry highlighting the relevant components of the target, moderators, and guides present in the MCNP model [1].

The present Cold Source moderator (CS) in SINQ has a 20 liter volume. This CS is filled with liquid D_2 and reduces the neutron energy to a colder spectrum. To enhance the number of emitted cold neutrons, a Re-Entrant hole (REH) has been attempted in the geometry. The REH should remove scattering and absorbing material between the spot with the maximum cold neutron flux (CS center) and the direction of the guide hall (Figure 49) [1].

In the following chapter, some possible solutions to increase effectiveness are presented. The advantages and disadvantages of the individual proposals are also discussed and assessed.

8.1 INCREASING OF THE BEAM ON SINQ

As already emerged from the simulation, it requires more energy in the moderator to implement a phase change in the small operation area. Otherwise, it could be achieved with an increased beam power on the spallation source SINQ. The advantage of this methodology is that the moderator would be easy to realize and it is reliable as it is a passive device, which does not need to be actively heated. In case of SINQ the present one would not need to be modified. The disadvantages of this procedure outweigh, since the phase change only works with a significantly increased beam current, which is not achievable with the present design of target and accelerator. The fact that the moderator performance depends on the beam current, has in general clear disadvantages. The neutron flux is then not proportional anymore to the beam current, since above a certain current the moderator works more efficient than before. It is likely that this effect is not observed immediately, but with some delay as it is a temperature effect, which needs time. Since the proton current trips a hundred times a

week, this would affect the measurements significantly. Even worse, since the gain factor of the moderator depends on the neutron energy, the neutron flux cannot be corrected by a simple constant factor. The availability of a required neutron energy varies in the moderator because of the filling of vapour in the Re-Entrant hole. Besides this, it is likely that the temperature distribution in the moderator is further influenced by the beam distribution and position on the target as well as the present target design.

The CFD simulations in this report seems to indicate that the content of the REH in the present moderator design becomes gaseous with a significantly increased beam current, not available yet with the present accelerator setup and target design, which would trigger a large investment and R&D. Besides this, as the current CFD simulations have to implement approximations and the 2-phase dynamics is a complex process, the prediction of the beam current needed is uncertain. A multi-phase model would be needed for a better prediction.

Altogether it can be concluded that the dependence of the moderator performance on the beam current has a couple of disadvantages and should be avoided. Besides this, increasing the beam current is not simply possible. Therefore, this solution does not appear to be practical.

8.2 RELOCATION OF THE COLD SOURCE MODERATOR

Another possibility would be to move the Cold Source Moderator closer to the spallation source SINQ (Figure 50).

Figure 50 Relocation of the Cold Source Moderator closer to the Spallation Source SINQ

However, from a technical point of view, this is very difficult to implement and can be achieved only with considerable structural replacement. In this case, the desired increase of the energy input to the Cold Source moderator is also dependent on the current-dependent beam on the SINQ target. Here, too, the disadvantages as described in chapter 8.1 predominate, especially due to the very expensive

replacement. In addition, there is the aspect of safety within this concept, because the Cold Source moderator is closer to the proton beam with higher temperature and structural loads.

8.3 INSTALLATION OF AN INTERNAL HEATING SOURCE

Another measure to obtain the desired vapour in the “Vapour Chamber” or the Re-Entrant hole (REH) would be the installation of an internal heat source directly in the “Vapour Chamber” (Figure 51).

Figure 51 Geometry changing from the Original REH to a REH with a Heating Block

There are two possibilities for the internal heat source:

1. One possibility would be the installation of an internal heat source of a dense medium, which absorbs the energy of the beam in the block and transfer it to the deuterium. The advantage of this possibility would be its simple construction. However, as in the previous descriptions, the disadvantage is the current-dependent energy supply via the beam to the SINQ target.
2. The second option is to install an independent heat source. The evaporation of the liquid deuterium would no longer be coupled to the current-dependent beam. The disadvantage of this option lies in the installation of a heating element and the connection to it. Furthermore, this element would also be prone to failures due to e.g. the high radiation and subsequent radiation damage. A simple repair would then not be feasible.

. In addition, with both options it has to be ensured that a larger fraction of the neutrons are not absorbed or up-scattered in the heating block or the heating element, which would reduce the flux and shift the energy spectrum.

Figure 52 Installation of a internal Heating Source (Heating Block).

8.4 INSTALLATION OF AN EXTERNAL HEATING SOURCE

Instead of an internal heat source, an external heat source could also be considered. The advantage here would be the simple installation on the Moderator Chamber (Figure 53), as well as the decoupling of the heat input under the “Vapour Chamber” compared to the energy input exerting from the beam. At the same time, however, it is difficult to install the heating source in such a way that the volume at the entrance of the neutron guide is heated. It would also be important that thermal contact with the Moderator Chamber is guaranteed. The disadvantage of this consideration is also the installation of feed cables and the reliability, as well as the difficult repair possibility, which likely would have to be performed by remote handling due to the large dose rate. What is disregarded are the structural stresses that can occur due to the thermal energy input.

Figure 53 Geometry changing from the Original REH to REH with a External Heating

Figure 54 Installation of a external Heating Source

8.5 CLOSED RE-ENTRANT HOLE (REH)

Another option would be to install a closed Re-Entrant hole (REH) (Figure 55). For this purpose, the REH can either be vacuumed or filled with a gas. The closed space has the advantage that it would be independent of the beam current. In the case of a gas-filled Re-Entrant hole, however, it must also be ensured that the gas does not condense, under the cryogenic conditions. In addition, the external pressure acting on the closed REH and thus the structural forces must also be taken into account. If a hole occurs during operation, the effectiveness of the installation would no longer be given. This cause of failure could only be noticed indirectly during operation through a decrease in the number of neutrons. A repair would be very difficult due to high activation of the device.

Figure 55 Geometry changing from the Original REH to Closed REH.

Figure 56 Installation of a closed REH

8.6 RE-DESIGN OF THE COLD SOURCE MODERATORS WITH THE "RE-ENTRANT BOX"

From the considerations and the simulations it quickly became clear that the very complex and difficult handling of the cryogenic phase change had to be decoupled from the beam current.

In order to make the phase change process independent of the beam power, it is advisable to decouple the "Re-Entrant Box" according to chapter 8.5. In addition, the shape of the REH and the surrounding materials can be optimized. Bergmann et al. [1] illustrates very well how such a solution can look like and which effective increase in performance can be expected from it.

To study the effect of different shapes of the REH on the neutron spectrum, neutrons are transported from the Cold Source moderator to the instruments via neutron guides (Figure 49) 6 m away. The neutron Guides are internally coated with neutron supermirrors, which are reflective to neutrons at low energies and low incident angles [1]. Therefore, for this a patched version of MCNP is used that can model neutron mirror reflections with the McStas reflectivity model [27]. Since the probability to feed the neutrons through the small neutron guide is small compared to all other processes, the statistics would be not sufficient. Therefore, the angle-integrated flux exiting 6 meters of the neutron guide was obtained with the help of precomputed energy- and angle-dependent transfer function, which correlates the angle and energy of an incoming neutron with one that exits the guide. These transfer functions are multiplied with the angular neutron flux at the entry of the guide and summed over angle to give a good approximation of the exiting neutron flux for rectangular guides [1]. A detailed description of the method using transfer functions can be found in [28].

In this study the strategy is to increase the neutron output to instruments without additional proton current on the spallation target SINQ.

Figure 57 The current REH geometry (Left). The REH geometry from the parametric scan (Middle). The REH geometry from the genetic optimization (Right) [1].

During the optimization, the various suggested geometries were simulated in comparison to the original geometry. The original geometry (REH Original) is shown in Figure 57 (Left). In the CFD simulation, the original geometry was examined very intensively in order to understand the associated phase change process. In order to decouple this process, two geometry variants were investigated that decouple the “Re-Entrant Box” from this process. For this purpose, the “Re-Entrant Box” were integrated directly into the moderator as windows and their shape varied.

The first variant of the new design (Figure 57 Middle) was called "Scan REH". This variant was determined by doing the most powerful combination of a parametric scan of the REH geometry. Two scans were carried out; one in the horizontal plane and one in the vertical plane. In both scans, the geometry was kept symmetrical about the midline.

The second variant (Figure 57 Right) was determined with the help of the DEAP framework for genetic optimization [29]. The variant is named "genetic REH".

The Figure of Merit (FOM) in all the optimization studies was chosen to be the total current exiting the AMOR/SANS-I guide six meters from the Cold Source surface from 3 to 6 Å, with the wavelength band which is useful for most of the instruments in the guide halls (Figure 49) [30].

Figure 58 [LEFT] The calculated spectra in the AMOR/SANS-I guide at the 6 m position (Left), and the gain curves for the Original REH, Scan REH, and Genetic REH geometries compared the case where the Original REH is filled with liquid D₂ (Right) [1].

Figure 58 shows the calculated spectra exiting the 6 m length of guide leading towards AMOR/SANS-I. Additional to this comparison of the different geometry variations, the gain over the original geometry with empty (“REH Original”) and filled with liquid D₂ („Filled“) is shown. It shows that the new designs produce gain curves that are significantly higher than that of the original design (REH Original).

The gain curve of the „Genetic REH“ has a slightly higher peak value (1.42 vs. 1.39) and a slightly higher average value from 3-6 Å (1.32 vs. 1.30), but has lower gains for wavelengths longer than 7 Å.

In addition, since different materials differ significantly in neutron absorption cross sections, which again depend on the neutron energy, it is promising to pay attention on the choice of the material. The combination of the developed geometry and different materials are also described by Bergmann et al. [1] and shown in Figure 59. Many options were considered, but only a few materials made sense.

The examined materials were carried out with the geometry “Scan REH”.

The list of cases was investigated and compared in Figure 59:

- 1) Adding cryogenic Be windows at the REH [31] to reflect small wavelength neutrons back into the moderator while allowing long wavelength neutrons to exit freely;
Result: The cold beryllium windows show a slight gain for wavelengths longer than 4 Å, and losses for wavelengths between 2 and 4 Å. Due to the losses in the wavelength range of interest, and the gains for short wavelengths (contribute to background), the beryllium windows are unattractive for the upgrade.
- 2) Adding a Pb-208 reflector [32], which has very low neutron absorption, to the back side of the Cold Source in order to reduce upscattering on the surrounding warm D2O;
Result: The Pb-208 reflector gives about a 5% gain uniformly. The implementation of such a heavy mass and acquisition of pure material could prove to be difficult.
- 3) Making the moderator be 100% ortho-D2 in order to increase the macroscopic cross section;
Result: The moving to a 100% ortho-D2 moderator would give about a 5% decrease for neutrons between 2 and 3.7 Å, a 5% increase for neutrons between 3.7 and 5.5 Å, and a 10% increase for longer wavelengths. Such a moderator could be realized with small recirculation loop in the storage volume constantly flowing the liquid D2 over a converter material (like iron oxide [33]).
- 4) Replacing the Zr safety hull with AlMg3, which has a lower total macroscopic cross section.
Result: Replacing the zirconium hull with the same thickness of AlMg3 gives 7% increase for neutrons less than 5.5 Å. If this is acceptable due to safety implications has yet to be seen.

Figure 59 [LEFT] The calculated neutron spectra in the AMOR/SANS-I guide at the 6 m position, and [RIGHT] the gain curves over the filled Original REH from material modifications [1].

8.7 COMPARISON OF POSSIBLE STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING THE NEUTRON OUTPUT

The options presented are summarized in the Table 18 based on advantages and disadvantages. This summary shows that the above proposed concept of the internally installed REH only makes sense if the efficiency of the new moderator design is independent of the beam current. It was already shown in the CFD simulations that reaching the necessary energy deposition for the phase change is not possible at the present maximum beam current, which is feasible. In any case, this means that a drop in beam current leads to a non-proportional and energy dependent drop in the neutron flux. An important criterion for the evaluation of the possibilities is the decoupling of moderator performance from the beam current on SINQ combined with simple and reliable construction – given the harsh environment of radiation.

	Advantage	Disadvantage
Original Re-Entrant Hole (REH)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feasibility of the gas phase in the REH not under the existing beam conditions Dependent on the beam current Small operating range¹ Loss of 20-40% neutron flux
Increasing of the beam on SINQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of existing moderator geometry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large investment in target development Large investment in accelerator leading to more power consumption

¹ Start of the operation range with beam current at which the phase change in the REH starts

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependent on the beam current • Small operation range¹ • Higher temperature and structural loads
Relocation of the Cold Source moderator		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs reshuffling of the complete infrastructure with shielding, etc. • Large investment • Dependent on the beam current • Small working range¹
Installation of an internal Heating Block	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple geometry design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependent on the beam current • Well understanding of heating & cryogenic processes • Study of influence on neutron spectrum • Small working range¹
Installation of an internal Heating Source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent on the beam current • Large working range² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feed-through of cables • Failure-prone to radiation • Dismantling & repair difficult due to high radiation • Study of influence on neutron spectrum
Installation of an external Heating Source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent on the beam current • Large working range² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feed-through of cables • Failure-prone to radiation • Repair difficult due to high radiation • Higher temperature and structural loads, due to the direct contact area
Closed Re-Entrant Hole (REH)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple geometry design • Independent on the beam current • Large working range² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to repair • Difficult to monitor vacuum conditions • Increased mechanical stress

² Start of the operation range with first beam current

Scan REH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple geometry design³ • Independent on the beam current • Large working range² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slightly more complex production • Increased mechanical stress
Genetic REH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple geometry design³ • Independent on the beam current • Large working range² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slightly more complex production • Increased mechanical stress

Table 18 Advantages and Disadvantages of the proposed measure for increasing the neutron flux.

When considering the advantages and disadvantages, there are three possible geometry variants that are suitable for increasing the neutron flux with the decoupling of the proton beam. Since monitoring and reliable design of the “Closed REH” also turns out to be more difficult, the two variants of the REH windows to be integrated directly into the moderator would be preferable. The "Genetic REH" variant shows a minimal increase in performance compared to the "Scan REH" variant. CFD and FEM simulations as well as mechanical engineering have to show, if from the cooling, stress and stability point of view the theoretical design with the required materials can be realized to further increase the moderator's performance.

³ Re-Entrant hole is directly integrated into the moderator as windows

9. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

In this report it is shown for the first time, why the cold moderator in SINQ does not have the performance as it was designed for. For this, complex CFD simulations were performed, which will help to design a new moderator of modified and optimized geometry targeting a gain factor of up to 1.5 dependent on the neutron energy. This would lead to an increase of the cold neutron flux by this factor without additional energy consumption, just by increasing the overall target efficiency of SINQ. In conclusion, this work contributed significantly to the understanding of the present moderator design, which is a prerequisite towards the increase of the efficiency of the target station.

As a starting point the CFD simulations implemented the spatially resolved energy deposition, which originates from particle transport Monte-Carlo simulations, as User-Defined Functions (UDFs). This UDFs were programmed in a way such that the current dependent energy deposition could be used. Due to the complexity of the geometry and the resulting requirements for solving physical equations by discretization using the Finite Volume Method, a separation of the solid body (moderator chamber) and the fluid body (fluid) was pursued.

The simulations have shown that the energy deposition both in the fluid and the surrounding AlMg3 moderator chamber is too low to fill the Internal Vapour Chamber, also called Re-Entrant Hole or short REH, with the vapour phase of the deuterium. When considering the AlMg3 moderator chamber in addition, the energy deposition will come closer to the area of the phase change. However, a coupling of the two phases of deuterium in a multiphase model taking radiation into account, need to be developed for a more accurate and reliable prediction.

With the results of the simulations, important knowledge about the behavior of the deuterium under the cryogenic conditions could be obtained, which is important for a new design. Further, considerations about the strategy of a new design and guidelines were already made. Since the performance of the present moderator design is strong dependent on the beam current, it is argued that this situation should be avoided a second time to provide a better performance not only at the highest currents. Since the proton beam current is not constant but drops frequently, the energy dependent neutron flux would not be proportional to the beam current anymore. Therefore, an important awareness is that the process of phase change in the “re-entrant box” is either supported by an external auxiliary measure, such as an additional heating element or by designing the REH as empty evacuated box in the moderator. Another possibility to get the required energy on the moderator would be to reduce the radius to the SINQ target axis. However, due to the severely limited space, this is not recommended and would result in a major reconstruction of the spallation source. The resulting increase in energy deposition is also kept within limits, since, as it is dependent on the beam current.

The aim should be to decouple this “re-entrant box” from the evaporation process to be independent on the beam current or the specific target design. In the work by Bergmann et al. [1] two possible geometries are presented that decouple the “re-entrant box” from the geometry and the cryogenic cooling process. The geometry and material optimization were performed from the point of view of

neutron production only. Therefore, they should also be examined numerically using CFD working towards a technical layout, which can be built.

For this the final CFD simulation have to establish the direct link between the layered moderator chamber and the fluid. The outer vacuum chamber made presently of Zircalloy should also be taken into account. Linking these components in one simulation poses a great challenge to the discretization and the resulting computing power. In addition, for this approach one must also consider the energy transfer in the form of radiation between the components, e.g of the different layers of the vessel, with vacuum in between for better isolation. In the present work, the vacuum chamber and its energy deposition have not been examined, but should be mentioned in this report for the sake of completeness. The single-phase model used in this work is well suited to determine an initial estimate of the temperature distribution and the phases to be deduced from it. In the future, however, the aim is to use a much more complex multi-phase model that also allows a direct differentiation of the phase areas. For a more accurate understanding of the moderator it is necessary to develop a multiphase model for this cryogenic boundary conditions between 18 and 25 K. For this reason it is a big challenge to use an additional Multiphase-model, e.g. Eulerian Multiphase-model. In this work the necessary material data of the deuterium have already been brought in and shown in the tables.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CS	Cold Source
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institute
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes
REH	Re-Entrant Hole
SINQ	Swiss Spallation Neutron Source
UDF	User Defined Function
WF	Wall Function